

coping with COP30

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From Vulnerability to **Leadership**

Strategic Framework for Enhancing Negotiation Power of Bangladesh at COP30

Climate negotiations under the Conference of the Parties (COP) have become troublesome for achieving effective responses since the consistent impacts of climate change have been visualised. Bangladesh consistently ranks among the world's most climate-vulnerable nations, yet translating this vulnerability into negotiation gains has proven crucial. Successes under the Climate Vulnerable Forum (CVF) leadership, such as the "Midnight Survival Deadline" in 2020, rallying dozens of countries to strengthen NDCs, the Dhaka-Glasgow Declaration 2021 demanding firm 1.5°C commitments and balanced finance, and advocacy leading to the Loss and Damage Fund creation, demonstrate Bangladesh's diplomatic potential.

However, structural hurdles remain: small delegations, high turnover, limited technical and financial resources, and challenges in coalition coordination reduce the negotiation power of Bangladesh.

As COP-30 approaches in Belém, Brazil in November 2025 branded a COP of implementation. Inclusive transition, rules for carbon market, incentivising climate-aligned investment, national climate plans with clear and mobilised investment pathway are being negotiated at COP 30 that could shape and advance financial opportunities for climate-vulnerable countries, for Bangladesh.

Bangladesh needs to adopt a multi-sectoral and sophisticated approach for building strong negotiation capacity. This paper outlines 12 priority sectors drawn from the national strategies of Bangladesh and windows lessons from other vulnerable countries. Each targeted negotiation strategies, and cross-cutting tactics (coalition-building, narrative framing, high-level diplomacy, etc. maximise the negotiation power of Bangladesh. Achieving tangible outcomes on finance, technology transfer, adaptation, and other areas is critical both for Bangladesh and for keeping the Paris 1.5°C goal within reach.

Historical Performance Analysis: Bangladesh's COP Trajectory

CVF Leadership Achievements

Climate Vulnerable Forum (CVF) Presidencies: Bangladesh uniquely chaired the CVF twice 2011 to 2013 and 2022 to 2024 (ICCCAD, 2024). Under the former regime, the CVF achieved several breakthroughs. For example, Bangladesh launched the “Midnight Survival Deadline” in 2020, calling for all countries to strengthen their NDCs by Dec 31, 2020.

This initiative prompted about 70 nations to enhance their commitments by that deadline. The 2021 Dhaka-Glasgow Declaration compelled major emitters to uphold the 1.5°C target, submit significantly more ambitious NDCs, and deliver the

\$100 billion annual finance promise with a 50:50 balance between adaptation and mitigation. Persistent CVF advocacy (with Bangladesh at the helm) also helped secure the establishment of the Loss and Damage Fund which was agreed at COP27 and operationalised at COP28 (ICCCAD, 2024) .

Institutional Innovations

Bangladesh fostered new coordination mechanisms: the CVF-V20 Joint Multi-Donor Fund for climate projects, CVF Thematic Ambassadors, a Global Parliamentary Group linking lawmakers from vulnerable nations, and successful campaigns (e.g., creation of a UN Special Rapporteur on climate and human rights) . These initiatives raised Bangladesh's profile and strengthened diplomatic networks.

Persistent Challenges

Small delegation size & high negotiator turnover

Bangladesh (like many LDCs) often sends very small delegations and faces high staff/negotiator turnover, which limits its ability to cover multiple concurrent negotiation tracks.

Thin technical expertise for carbon markets

Complex dossiers such as Article 6 (carbon markets) and detailed finance frameworks require specialised technical and legal expertise that many LDC delegations lack.

Coalition coordination burdens and competing memberships with economic group

Bangladesh must balance multiple coalition memberships (e.g., LDC Group, CVF/V20, G77+China, plus alignment with AOSIS or the African Group), and divergent priorities across these blocs can make unified bargaining harder.

Limited budgets for preparatory work and legal assistance

Many developing country delegations, including Bangladesh have constrained budgets for pre-COP preparation and cannot afford sustained in-room technical/legal assistance, which weakens their negotiating

Persistent Challenges for Bangladesh in Climate Negotiations

Five interconnected barriers limiting negotiating effectiveness

capacity.

Logistical pressure / early departures reduce “voice” in late-night plenaries

Small teams with limited resources often must leave sessions early (or cannot cover simultaneous late-night informal consultations), reducing their presence/“voice” in late negotiating hours and lowering leverage.

Priority Sectors for COP-30 Negotiations

Bangladesh’s strategic interests (NDC, NAP, national plans) and global context suggest a focus on 12 key areas. For each, we outline why it matters, current gaps, negotiation demands, potential coalitions, and preparation needed.

1. Climate Finance Architecture and the New Collective Quantified Goal (NCQG)

Why It Matters: COP-30 is widely seen as the “Finance COP,” where parties will finalise the New Collective Quantified Goal (NCQG) on climate finance for 2025–2030 (United Nations Climate Change, 2025) . For Bangladesh, inadequate finance is the central hurdle: the country needs roughly \$176 billion to implement its NDC by 2030 (The Daily Star, 2024), yet only a fraction of even the original \$100 billion target has been delivered. Globally, adaptation finance is abysmally low (only about 21% of public climate finance goes to adaptation (World Economic Forum, 2021) and ~71% of reported climate finance flows are loans, not grants (Oxfam International, 2022). With Bangladesh’s high climate vulnerability, these imbalances compound debt risks and leave adaptation needs unmet. The COP-30 outcome on NCQG will shape finance flows for the next decade and is thus existential for

Priority Sectors for COP-30 Negotiations

Strategic Framework for Bangladesh and LDCs

Bangladesh's resilience.

Current Gaps: Developed countries only met their long-standing \$100 billion climate finance pledge in 2022, according to OECD data, providing \$115.9 billion in total.

However, only about one-quarter (around \$32 billion) of this supported adaptation, while the majority was directed toward mitigation efforts (Oxfam International, 2022). Moreover, most climate finance continues to be delivered as loans rather than grants, further deepening debt burdens in climate-vulnerable developing countries.

Meanwhile, its financing needs far exceed global pledges—an AAB (2022) analysis estimates the country will require roughly \$480 billion per year by 2030 to implement comprehensive climate action. In sum, both the scale (total volume), quality (grant share and adaptation balance), and accessibility of international climate finance remain deeply inadequate for meeting Bangladesh's urgent needs.

Negotiation Strategy:

- **Quantum and Quality:** Bangladesh should argue for a highly ambitious NCQG that reflects actual needs: on the order of \$1–1.3 trillion per year by 2030 (including public and private flows). While official COP text envisages up to \$1.3 trillion by 2035, the case for Bangladesh would be strengthened by its own needs assessment (Drishti IAS, 2025). The country should insist the NCQG adopt at least a \$100 billion floor and automatic scaling linked to the Global Stocktake (as per the Glasgow decision). Crucially, Bangladesh must fight for parity (50:50) between adaptation and mitigation finance (UNFCCC, n.d.), reversing the current 80:20 split in favour of mitigation. At least

half of adaptation finance should be grants (to avoid deepening debt).

Bangladesh can also demand integration of debt relief provisions: for instance, climate finance allocations could relieve debt servicing or come with debt-swap options, easing fiscal strain as highlighted by civil society reports.

Access Mechanisms: Bangladesh should champion direct access modalities and decentralisation of funds. This includes strengthening the Adaptation Fund and Green Climate Fund (GCF) to channel more resources through national implementing entities, rather than multilateral intermediaries.

It should push for simplified application and disbursement procedures tailored to LDCs and small island states (SIDS), including rapid disbursement for emergencies.

A major demand will be dedicated funding windows for locally-led adaptation (LLA), allowing communities like women and adolescent girls, local governments, and Indigenous peoples to access funds directly for grassroots projects.

Transparency & Accountability: Bangladesh should insist on clear definitions and robust tracking: for example, distinguishing “new and additional” climate finance from Official Development Assistance (ODA), and requiring reporting on grant vs. loan. Calls for an independent monitoring mechanism (potentially under the IMF or COP secretariat) that tracks NCQG disbursement and adherence to the agreed adaptation-mitigation balance should be supported (UNFCCC, n.d.). Standardized transparency frameworks (e.g. the OECD's

guidelines) should be strengthened so we know who gets funds, for what purposes, and how effectively they are used.

Coalition Building: Bangladesh should form a coalition of finance-focused developing countries.

The LDC Group and AOSIS share a demand for more grants and adaptation share. African nations likewise need vast adaptation finance and will support resilience funding.

Bangladesh can also align with the broad G77+China negotiators who want equity-based finance. Building alliances with progressive developed countries (e.g. Netherlands, Sweden) on issues like climate justice and adaptation grants could also help push the envelope.

Preparation: Bangladeshi negotiators must prepare rigorous cost needs assessments and impact analyses.

For example, an updated national study should justify the \$176 billion 2030 NDC cost and detail sectoral breakdowns.

Cost-benefit research (e.g. from World Bank or UN reports) showing high returns on adaptation investment will help argue that funding is economically wise.

Bangladesh should document recent climate losses (e.g., the 2024 monsoon floods affected ~1.8 crore people, including 70 lakh children to illustrate financing gaps.

Economic analyses should also quantify how underfunding (e.g. only 21% adaptation) raises future costs, bolstering the case for scaling up finance.

Funding: 0.79% of \$100B Target

2. Loss and Damage Finance and Implementation

Why It Matters: The Loss and Damage (L&D) Fund, established at COP27 and operationalised at COP28, is a historic breakthrough for vulnerable nations. Bangladesh's advocacy was central to its creation.

However, pledged funds fall far short of needs. By COP28 held in 2023 only \$792 million (from 19 countries) had been pledged (Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung e.V., 2024), while Bangladesh alone suffered an estimated \$11.3 billion in climate losses in 2021 (AAB, 2024).

COP30 must ensure the L&D Fund is adequately capitalised, accessible, and attuned to Bangladesh's specific loss profiles.

Key Negotiation Points:

- **Capitalisation:** Bangladesh should press for a firm baseline target for the L&D Fund—for

example, a minimum of \$100 billion per year, reflecting historical emissions responsibility.

Contributions must be mandatory or strongly incentivised for high-income, high-emitting countries (UNFCCC, 2022). Bangladesh should champion innovative sources e.g. levies on international aviation and shipping, a financial transaction tax, or a small fossil-fuel extraction levy (as some proposals suggest) to generate predictable flows. Developing a "polluter pays" narrative can support these ideas (United Nations, 1992).

Governance and Access: The Fund's governance must centre on vulnerable countries. Bangladesh should demand equitable board representation and a voice for LDCs and CVF members. Critically, the Fund must have direct access windows for affected communities, NGOs, and local governments, with simplified procedures, not only for large projects. Emergency funding protocols are needed so resources can be quickly disbursed after disasters

(instead of only long-term recovery).

Bangladesh should also highlight the interim World Bank hosting arrangements: any onerous conditionalities or delays via the trustee (World Bank) role must be opposed.

Scope and Eligibility: Bangladesh should push for a broad definition of loss and damage. Consistent natural disasters like floods, cyclones must be funded, but so must slow-onset events: sea-level rise, salinisation, desertification.

Both economic losses (infrastructure, crops) and non-economic losses (cultural heritage, territory) should qualify. Additionally, funds must cover climate-induced displacement. This includes internal relocation costs and preparing for cross-border movements.

Bangladesh-specific Evidence:

To make a compelling case, Bangladesh should present detailed loss assessments. For example, the massive 2024 floods affected around 1.8 crore people with infrastructural damages and chronic coastal erosion threatening villages underscore the scale of damage.

Data on agricultural losses from salinity or disaster-related migration costs should be documented. Highlighting personal stories (e.g. climate migrants) can humanize the losses alongside statistics.

Preparation and Coalition: Build on Bangladesh's CVF leadership on loss and damage.

As part of CVF/V20, Bangladesh can convene working groups to draft Fund implementation recommendations (drawing on the Loss and Damage Fund Board's

progress reports). Coalition-wise, align with AOSIS and Africa for pushing mandatory finance; with the G77+China on innovative finance sources; and with research bodies like ICCCAD to refine Bangladesh's L&D proposals.

3. Adaptation Finance and NAP Implementation

Strategic Context: National Adaptation Plan of Bangladesh (2023–2050) lays out six strategic goals: disaster protection; climate-resilient agriculture; climate-smart cities; nature-based biodiversity conservation; governance integration; and transformative capacity-building (Climate Change Laws of the World, 2022).

Achieving these requires sustained adaptation funding. However, current flows are far below needs: global adaptation finance must at least double by 2025 (as pledged at COP26) to approach parity with mitigation (UNFCCC, n.d.). COP30 is a moment to operationalize those commitments.

Negotiation Focus:

- **Double Adaptation Finance:** Bangladesh should insist that developed countries fulfill COP26 promises to double adaptation finance by 2025. It must demand this increase be concrete (with pledged amounts) and frontloaded.

Dedicated NAP Funding: Advocate for a dedicated NAP implementation facility within the Green Climate Fund (GCF) or other multilateral channels.

This could include 5 to 10 years funding envelopes rather than piecemeal projects, allowing Bangladesh to implement long-term adaptation strategies. Precedents

Bangladesh NAP: Six Goals (2023-2050)

exist in other global funds (e.g. Global Environment Facility result frameworks).

Sector Priorities: Bangladesh should use COP-30 to highlight financing for key adaptation sectors:

Agriculture & Food Security: Funding for climate-smart agro tech (stress-tolerant seeds, precision irrigation, mechanization) is critical.

For example, saline-tolerant rice varieties and “floating agriculture” (as pioneered in Bangladesh) need scale-up (The Daily Star, 2024). Financial support for diversified livelihoods (e.g. fish–forest–fruit agroforestry models) and agro-insurance schemes should be sought. Bangladesh can cite successful pilot projects or World Bank case studies to justify scaled finance.

Water Resources: Bangladesh has undertaken massive infrastructure for water management (e.g. 726 km of riverbank protection, 1,266 km of embankment rehabilitation). It should seek international funding for finishing and maintaining such

projects, plus investing in ecosystem-based measures (wetland restoration, rainwater harvesting, watershed protection).

Coastal Zone & Ecosystems: The project mangrove restoration at coastal region in Bangladesh (over 9,650 ha planted) shows how natural defenses can reduce storm surge damage. COP-30 presents an opportunity to secure finance for expanding these “blue carbon” projects.

Bangladesh should call for dedicated climate fund windows for community mangrove afforestation and coastal wetland regeneration, given their dual adaptation/mitigation benefit .

Governance & Cross-Cutting: Bangladesh can push for integrated approaches. For instance, insisting that all GCF-funded projects include climate risk safeguards, and that climate adaptation be mainstreamed into development financing.

Bangladesh should also stress the importance of multilevel governance funding: supporting local government adaptation planning and early warning systems.

Coalitions: Work with countries having similar adaptation needs.

Coastal states like the Maldives or Vietnam share interests in coastal resilience, while the Netherlands brings delta-management expertise. The Climate Vulnerable Forum should present a united front on adaptation funding demands.

Technical Preparation: Bangladesh should prepare a “NAP investment plan” documenting sectoral costs and expected outcomes, backed by scientific and economic analysis.

For example, quantifying how every dollar in adaptation spares future losses (flood losses in 2024 being a case study) will make the funding question more persuasive .

4. Mitigation Ambition in NDC and Just Transition

Strategic Position: Though emission rate of Bangladesh is minuscule, around 0.56% of global carbon emission (Dhaka Tribune, 2025) , the country must show leadership by setting conditional mitigation targets and addressing equity issues.

The 2021 updated NDC commits to a 6.73% unconditional emissions reduction by

2030 in BAU and 15.12% conditional with finance/tech support (IEEFA, 2022). These conditional targets require an estimated \$176 billion over 2021–2030 (The Daily Star, 2024). Negotiations at COP-30 should thus tie Bangladesh’s mitigation to concrete international support, while framing climate action as a development opportunity.

Negotiation Focus:

- **Conditional Commitments:** Bangladesh should make it clear that its higher mitigation ambition is contingent on receiving adequate grants and clean technology. In COP discussions (e.g. Global Stocktake follow-up), Bangladesh can demand that these conditional goals be recognised and supported via enhanced finance and tech transfer. Conversely, Bangladesh should press major emitters to tighten their own NDCs to meet the 1.5°C target (drawing on CVF messaging (ICCCAD, 2024)).

Just Transition: The concept of a “just transition” in Bangladesh means something different from rich countries’ agenda. It means protecting the livelihoods of climate-affected communities and workers as the economy adapts.

Bangladesh should call for support to: retrain and re-employ people displaced by climate (e.g. coastal migrants) and workers

in sectors like agriculture. It should seek funding for social safety nets and livelihood programs (e.g. microcredit, skills training) targeting climate-vulnerable groups, especially women. Bangladesh should also emphasise gender equity in transition plans, aligning with the country's Climate Change Gender Action Plan and international norms (ICCCAD, 2022; AAB, 2024).

Sectoral Mitigation: In line with its NDC, Bangladesh should negotiate for international assistance to scale up renewables and efficiency: solar/wind projects, grid expansion, and demand-side measures. For example, Bangladesh's installed renewable capacity is still only ~1.4 GW, far from the 40% goal by 2041 (Enerdata, 2023). COP-30 can be used to secure concessional finance and technology (like storage, grid control) for renewables.

Bangladesh should also include nature-based mitigation: REDD+ credits from mangrove conservation and reforestation, which it can claim under Article 6 with robust safeguards. Methane reduction in agriculture (rice, livestock) and waste (landfill gas capture) are other priorities where technology transfer will be sought (IPCC, n.d.).

Citing Bangladesh's Contribution: To underscore fairness, Bangladesh can point out that developed countries are responsible for most cumulative emissions, yet vulnerable nations bear the brunt. Emphasising such equity arguments (and Bangladesh's tiny emission share (Dhaka Tribune, 2025)) reinforces demands for stronger global mitigation by others.

5. Technology Transfer and Innovation

Critical Needs: Bangladesh lags in access to

cutting-edge climate technologies, a gap that must be addressed to achieve its NDC and NAP. Barriers include high costs, intellectual property restrictions, and insufficient local capacity (World Economic Forum, 2021) .

Negotiation Priorities:

Strengthening the Technology Mechanism:

Bangladesh should call for increased funding and staffing of the UNFCCC's Climate Technology Centre and Network (CTCN), and for the creation of regional technology hubs (e.g. a South Asian green tech center under South-South cooperation). Streamlining Technology Needs Assessments (TNAs) is also key so countries can rapidly identify priorities.

Specific Tech Demands: Bangladesh should push for concessional access to priority technologies: advanced solar PV and wind generators (including local assembly lines), green hydrogen research, precision agriculture tools, climate-resilient seed breeding, water purification and desalination systems, and robust multi-hazard early warning systems with the help of satellite or AI-backed. Ideally, developed countries and technology providers would offer these on grant or soft loan terms, with training packages.

IPR and Pooling:

Bangladesh should advocate for flexible intellectual property solutions. This could include compulsory licensing for essential technologies (as practiced under TRIPS flexibilities), patent pools for climate tech (analogous to vaccine patent pools), or an IP waiver for key adaptation technologies.

Coalition: Form a technology alliance with other developing and emerging countries (e.g.

India, China, other South Asian and African nations) under the G77+China umbrella, to collectively demand IPR waivers and technology support. This block can leverage the argument that climate technology is a global public good for survival.

Preparation: Maintain an updated list of technology priorities (e.g. Bangladeshi tech needs assessment) and case studies demonstrating their impact. Bangladesh could pilot projects (e.g. demonstration solar grid in rural areas) and present success stories at COP to show readiness to absorb technology

6. Article 6 Carbon Markets and ITMOs

Context: Article 6 of the Paris Agreement (carbon markets) is operational but contentious, with concerns about integrity and equity (United Nations Climate Change, 2025). Bangladesh should engage here to both attract high-quality credit flows and safeguard against market abuses.

Negotiation Focus:

- **Environmental Integrity:** Bangladesh should align with the LDC and SIDS demand for strict rules: all Article 6 mechanisms must ensure real, additional emissions reductions with robust corresponding adjustments to avoid double-counting (UNFCCC, n.d.). Projects that damage local environments or communities (e.g. monoculture plantations) must be excluded.

Benefit-Sharing: Insist that Article 6.4 (the new market mechanism) include a share-of-proceeds (LDC Climate Change,

2021) diverted to adaptation or L&D funds (UNFCCC, n.d.) .

Host countries (like Bangladesh) should retain a fair share of credit revenues. Bangladesh can demand that any carbon credit project (e.g. a wind farm) must finance community development or go into a local climate fund.

Support for LDCs: Push for priority treatment of LDCs in Article 6.4 that simplified entry rules, technical help for writing methodologies, and safeguards against price volatility. The goal is to ensure the carbon market doesn't become another resource drain but actually channels revenue for sustainable development in Bangladesh.

Bangladesh Opportunities: Bangladesh can present specific carbon project ideas:

Blue Carbon Credits: Its vast mangrove belts sequester CO₂ (Bangladesh's plantings currently absorb ~0.965 million tons CO₂/year). These could be monetized via Article 6 credits if standards allow "blue carbon".

Renewable Energy Credits: Solar and wind projects that displace coal (e.g. the Rampal plant) can generate Article 6 credits. Bangladesh should secure buy-in from high-integrity buyers (EU carbon market, corporate purchasers) for such projects.

Forestry and AFOLU: Planting trees on unused lands, or improved rice cultivation, could create credits. Bangladesh should design these carefully to meet international safeguards.

Bangladesh should ensure its voice is heard in the Article 6 rulebook and post-2023 guidelines discussions.

Coalition: Working with other LDCs and African Group members to demand strict governance of Article 6, plus a share-of-proceeds for adaptation. AOSIS often leads on credit quality issues. Bangladesh should ensure its voice is heard in the Article 6 rulebook and post-2023 guidelines discussions.

7. Climate-Induced Migration and Displacement

Critical Issue: Bangladesh already faces large-scale climate displacement, yet international support and legal frameworks remain inadequate. By 2050, 19.9 million Bangladeshis could be internally displaced by climate impacts (MPI, 2024), and countless others may seek refuge abroad. At COP-30, Bangladesh must push migration to the forefront of climate talks.

Negotiation Focus:

- **International Framework:** Bangladesh can lead calls for a global regime on climate mobility.

This includes recognition (even informally) of climate migrations in international law, and building on the UN's Task Force on Displacement. Bangladesh should advocate creation of a protection framework (akin to the Nansen Initiative) specifically for cross-border climate migrants. This might involve climate-sensitive refugee status or regional compacts (e.g. with India and Myanmar) to manage flows humanely.

Dedicated Finance: Propose a displacement/migration window under the Loss & Damage Fund or a new multilateral vehicle. Such a fund would finance planned relocations (e.g. buying land for climate migrants), urban integration support (Dhaka receives ~2,000

rural migrants daily), and humanitarian needs arising from climate crises. Bangladesh can cite its National Strategy on Internal Displacement (2021) as a model for comprehensive response and ask for international support to implement it.

Case Study: Bangladesh should present its comprehensive displacement strategy, encompassing prevention, protection, and durable solutions, at COP-30, positioning it as a model for other Least Developed Countries (LDCs).

Recent climate events underscore the urgency of such measures: for example, the 2024 floods displaced approximately 18 million (1.8 crore) people (The Daily Star, 2024). This evidence can be used to highlight that climate-induced mobility represents an immediate humanitarian challenge, necessitating targeted climate finance and support, rather than being framed solely as a future risk.

Coalition: Form a "Migration and Climate" group within CVF or LDCs (perhaps with Pacific Islands, African Sahel states, and nearby countries with migration links). By framing climate migration as a global security/humanitarian concern, Bangladesh can engage non-traditional allies like UN agencies, development banks, civil society.

8. Gender-Responsive Climate Action

Why It Matters: In Bangladesh, women are disproportionately vulnerable to climate change due to poverty, limited rights, and social roles (AAB, 2024) (ICCCAD, 2022). Yet global climate finance and policies often overlook gender. COP-30 is an opportunity to advance gender justice in climate action.

Evidence: The majority of Bangladeshi

women are poor and largely dependent on climate-sensitive resources; water, forests, agriculture, etc. (AAB, 2024). They also face barriers to early warning and shelters, and their informal livelihoods suffer most from disasters (AAB, 2024). Research shows climate projects often exclude women or fail to assess gender impacts.

Negotiation Focus:

- Gender-Responsive Finance: Bangladesh should demand that at least 30% of international climate finance (GCF, Adaptation Fund, L&D Fund) be earmarked for gender-responsive projects (AAB, 2024). It should advocate creating a dedicated gender facility within major climate funds and requiring gender impact assessments for all funded programs.

Leadership & Participation: Bangladesh should push for support to build women's leadership in climate policy. This includes funding for women-led adaptation initiatives (e.g. women's farmer groups using climate-smart techniques), and training programs for female negotiators from developing countries (AAB, 2024). COP-30 could endorse quotas for gender balance on UNFCCC bodies and boards.

Integrated Sectors: Highlight gender in specific sectors: e.g., in agriculture finance programs, ensure rural women farmers can access credit and technology; in disaster risk reduction, design early-warning systems with women's communication channels;

in migration/displacement planning, ensure protections for women and girls. Bangladesh can cite its Climate Change Gender Action Plan (2022) and successful projects (like women's cooperatives in coastal areas) as evidence.

9. Nature-Based Solutions and Ecosystem Restoration

Strategic Opportunity: COP-30 that has been hosted in Brazil (Amazon basin), there will be emphasis on nature-based solutions (NbS). Bangladesh has strong credentials here: it has planted over 9,650 hectares of mangroves on the coast, protecting millions from storms and sequestering ~965,000 tons of CO₂ annually.

These successes make Bangladesh a natural advocate for NbS at COP-30. Benefits: Bangladesh's mangroves have been shown to reduce wave heights and erosion significantly, while boosting fisheries and creating livelihoods (especially for women crab-farmers). Ecosystem restoration also provides carbon credits (blue carbon) which can be sold or counted toward NDCs.

Bangladesh should seek a dedicated funding window for NbS within the GCF/ Adaptation Fund.... recognizing that ecosystems take time to mature

Negotiation Focus:

-Dedicated NbS Finance: Bangladesh should seek a dedicated funding window for NbS within the GCF/ Adaptation Fund, with long-term financing (10–20 years) recognizing that ecosystems take time to mature.

It should also demand that NbS be recognized in both adaptation and

mitigation finance (to allow “double-counting” for the same action).

Technical Standards: Advocate for developing standardized methodologies for NbS under Article 6 (so that mangrove projects can credibly generate carbon credits) and for NbS best-practice guidelines (with community involvement). Bangladesh can collaborate with organizations like IUCN’s NbS Alliance on this.

Priority Projects: In COP pitches, Bangladesh should highlight specific sites for expansion (e.g. the identified areas in the Sundarbans delta) and initiatives like urban reforestation (Dhaka is expanding green space) . Wetland and coral restoration (blue carbon) projects deserve funding too.

Coalition: Join forces with other mangrove-restoring nations (Indonesia, Philippines) and with Amazon Basin countries on biodiversity or NbS agendas. CVF can include an “NbS caucus” of vulnerable countries. Given Brazil’s focus, Bangladesh should coordinate with the Brazilian COP presidency to align on ecosystem issues (UNFCCC, 2025).

10. Blue Economy and Ocean-Climate Nexus

Emerging Opportunity: Beyond mangroves, Bangladesh’s coastal waters and maritime claims offer untapped climate-resilient development (the “blue economy”). Bangladesh’s extended

Exclusive Economic Zone (118,813 km²) provides space for fisheries, aquaculture, and potentially offshore renewables (The World Bank, 2017). Integrating climate policy with ocean stewardship is crucial.

Climate-Ocean Challenges: Rising sea temperatures and acidification threaten Bangladesh’s fisheries and coral reefs . Saltwater intrusion damages coastal agriculture. Cyclones worsen marine pollution (plastics, sewage) that also harm human health.

Opportunities & Priorities:

- **Sustainable Fisheries:** COP30 discussions on “Forests, Oceans & Biodiversity” are a chance to push for climate-adaptive fisheries finance: e.g. support for coastal fishing communities to adopt sustainable gear, fish sanctuaries (which also serve as breeding grounds), and disaster-proofing of small boats and harbors.

Aquaculture & Blue Carbon: Bangladesh can highlight seaweed farming and coastal aquaculture (prawn, tilapia in ponds) as livelihoods that absorb CO₂. Restoring seagrass meadows (blue carbon stores) can be a mitigation/adaptation double win. International funding should flow to scale these community-based ventures.

Offshore Renewables: The Bay of Bengal has wind and tidal potential. Bangladesh should seek partnerships (and climate finance) for offshore wind pilot projects. Technology transfer for wave energy or marine solar platforms could also be explored.

Marine Conservation: Argument for GEF or GEF-financed marine protected areas and coral rehabilitation projects. Climate funds can integrate ocean targets (building on UN Ocean Decade goals).

Bangladesh can propose including the Sundarbans (mangrove and estuarine ecosystem) in international conservation schemes with climate funding.

Negotiation Position: The demand of COP30 climate finance architecture explicitly includes “blue economy” lines. That might mean blue economy components in NDCs and NAPs should be recognized by donors. COP side events or pavilion exhibits could showcase the holistic coastal resilience model on mangroves and sustainable fisheries of Bangladesh.

events. COP-30 negotiators can highlight these needs, arguing that donors should not neglect them in favor of capitals.

Tech & Knowledge: Advocate for international partnerships on urban climate tools: urban heat mapping, resilient transport, and smart water management systems.

11. Urban Climate Resilience Emerging Challenges: Bangladesh is urbanizing rapidly, Dhaka only consisting of more than ~22 million today (The Financial Express, 2025). Mega cities are experiencing hazardous events consistently. Dhaka suffers severe heat islands, flooding, waterlogging, pollution, and infrastructure that strain around 2,000 new daily climate migrants (UNDRR, 2023). Urban resilience is often underfunded globally, yet essential for Bangladesh’s future.

Bangladesh should lobby for a commitment that a share of climate finance flows be earmarked for capacity building...

Bangladesh should leverage networks (like C40 cities) to bring foreign expertise to its cities.

Nature-Based Urban Solutions: Push for inclusion of urban green infrastructure in climate funding (e.g. parks to mitigate flooding and heat). Bangladesh can cite Dhaka’s plan to increase green space by 70% and ask for technical/financial help.

Policy Integration: Bangladesh can propose that its city climate strategies be integrated into NAP/ NDC frameworks. For example, urban adaptation plans submitted to UNFCCC could become project pipelines for GCF.

Negotiation Focus:

- **Urban Adaptation Finance:** Push for a dedicated urban climate resilience fund window. Climate funds traditionally focus on national projects, but Bangladesh should argue for sub-national and city-level grants.

This could support upgrading slum infrastructure (drainage, solar streetlights, resilient housing), climateproofing schools/hospitals, and strengthening city disaster response.

Secondary Cities: The growth rate of sub-urban areas of Bangladeshis increasing and these areas need early help to combat climatic

12. Capacity Building and Knowledge Systems

Long-Term Imperative: Sustainable climate action requires skilled people and institutions. Yet capacity building is often neglected despite clear needs: Bangladesh has few climate scientists, meteorologists, negotiators, or legal experts, and its universities need climate curricula.

Negotiation Focus:

- **Institutional Funding:** Bangladesh should lobby for a commitment that a share of

climate finance flows be earmarked for capacity building, research, and institutions. For example, GCF could allocate funds to climate research centers (e.g. ICCCAD) as implementing entities.

South-South Networks: Need to propose a South Asian or CVF regional climate center to pool expertise. Negotiators could work with UNFCCC's Capacity-building Initiative for Transparency (CBIT) or new COP mechanisms (like a "global training hub").

Training and Talent: Bangladesh deliberately asks UNFCCC-related training programs (like UNITAR's LDC negotiator courses, eEuropean Capacity Building Initiative- ECBI training) to receive stable funding with quotas for Bangladeshi candidates. COP-30 could welcome pledges by development partners (commonwealth nations, EU, etc.) to sponsor such training.

Data and Technology: It's high time to push for international support in climate data infrastructure: better weather stations, national satellite receivers, hydro-meteorological modeling. Emphasize that early-warning and planning depend on these systems.

Inclusive Knowledge: Bangladesh should insist that local and indigenous knowledge be financed and included in climate plans (e.g. through community-based adaptation projects). COP decisions or funding criteria could formalize this integration.

Strategic Demand: In negotiations, frame capacity building as a discrete element of climate funding. For example: "X dollars of the NCQG should be set aside for building developing countries' climate research and negotiation capacity."

Cross-Cutting Negotiation Strategies:

Beyond technical demands, Bangladesh's success at COP-30 will hinge on smart tactics:

Coalition Building: Leverage Bangladesh's memberships in multiple blocs (LDC, CVF, G77+China, Asia Group) to project power. Well before COP-30, these coalitions should finalize unified position papers on Bangladesh's priorities (finance, L&D, etc.) . Use CVF's moral authority (1.5°C cause) and LDC's solidarity on adaptation to amplify Bangladesh's voice.

Daily in-session caucuses, quick communication channels (WhatsApp groups), and rotating spokespersons can keep positions coherent. Bangladesh can also seek issue-based alliances beyond traditional groups: for example, teaming with small progressive countries (Norway on climate transparency), or with faith-based and youth networks to broaden support.

Borrowing Power: To overcome its limitations, Bangladesh should "borrow" authority from respected partners. For instance, Bangladesh can commission analysis from IPCC or academics (e.g. from IIED, WRI, ICCCAD) and cite it in negotiations (ICCCAD, 2024 ; UNFCCC, n.d.). In COP debates, technical experts from these institutes can brief delegates, bolstering Bangladesh's credibility. Civil society and media outreach also matter:

Bangladesh can coordinate with NGOs (AAB, CARE) to publicize its demands during COP, using op-eds, social media, and press conferences (The Daily Star, 2024 ; MPI, 2024).

Collaboration with the private sector (green investors, tech firms) can showcase Bangladesh's "bankable" climate projects, signaling that finance to Bangladesh yields returns.

Even legal experts could be engaged – e.g. referencing International Court of Justice findings on climate rights – to frame Bangladesh's case as grounded in global norms.

Narrative Framing and Storytelling: Bangladesh must control the narrative. The country should assert its identity as a "frontline nation" – a leader and innovator, not a mere victim. It can highlight success stories (floating farms, community early warning) alongside its suffering. Messages like "1.5°C is survival, not luxury" or "Climate Justice Now" can resonate. Human stories (e.g. mothers displaced by floods) backed by hard data (1.8 crore people flooded in 2024, children's mortality stats) make an emotional impact. By branding itself "Bangladesh: Science, Solutions, Survival" in speeches and events, Bangladesh can shift perception to a provider of solutions.

Technical Preparedness: The Bangladesh delegation must enter COP-30 with detailed groundwork. This includes briefs on all agenda items (finance, Article 6, adaptation, etc.), draft negotiation text proposals, and clear fallback positions. Negotiators should have up-to-date data on climate impacts: e.g. quantified losses from recent disasters, sectoral adaptation needs, NDC cost breakdowns. They should be fluent in UNFCCC procedures and ready to intervene strategically (right of reply, etc.). Simulations and pre-COP training (perhaps in partnership with European Capacity Building Initiative- ECBI or UNITAR) will sharpen their tactics.

High-Level Engagement: The leaders of Bangladesh should use COP30 political moments. The Chief Adviser of the interim government, Prof. Dr. Muhammad Yunus, or a senior climate minister should speak at the high-level segment and any Leaders Summit in Belém, delivering Bangladesh's key demands.. Bilateral diplomacy is crucial:

Bangladesh must schedule meetings between its ministerial team and peers (U.S., EU countries, China, India, Brazil as host). A CVF Summit (virtual or side-event) could convene vulnerable-nation leaders to present a unified platform. Media outreach by high-level figures will garner publicity. In short, mix persistent pressure with outreach: e.g. congratulate any real climate aid or tech transfer from a donor, while publicly noting deficits elsewhere.

Bridging Development and Environment: Bangladesh can position itself as a partner in solving climate challenges. Propose specific pilot projects (e.g., a climate-resilient rural electrification initiative with Netherlands or UNDP) as concrete cooperation examples. This "we can do it together" approach may soften resistance.

Bangladesh could also publicly acknowledge positive steps by developed countries (say, confirming a new pledge) to encourage more generosity ("give credit when due" approach). At the same time, Bangladesh must never lose focus on equity: it can frame its demands as supporting developed countries' own climate credibility (e.g. "Investing in Bangladesh in adaptation is investing in the global 1.5°C goal"). Aligning with COP-30 Themes: Finally, leverage the specific context of Belém 2025. Brazil's presidency emphasizes implementation, nature, and inclusion. Bangladesh's focus on concrete finance, NbS, and social issues like

migration, gender, etc. dovetails with these themes. For example, on “Forests & Oceans” day, Bangladesh can jointly advocate with Brazil for global mangrove restoration. On “Human & Social Development” day, Bangladesh leads on migration and gender. Embedding Bangladesh’s agenda within Brazil’s action-oriented posture will amplify relevance.

Conclusion: From Vulnerability to Leadership

Bangladesh experiences an existential climate crisis – sea-level rise, cyclones, floods and salinity threaten up to 19.9 million people by mid-century (MPI, 2024). Yet vulnerability also confers moral authority and urgency. COP-30 must be the moment Bangladesh transforms that authority into real support on the ground. The country’s demands are clear and actionable: for example, an NCQG of at least \$1+ trillion annually with 50% to adaptation (mostly as grants), a well-funded Loss and Damage Fund (aiming for \$100 billion/year), robust technology transfer (with IPR flexibilities), recognition and funding for climate migration, and long-term financing for proven solutions like mangrove restoration. COP-30 must be the moment for Bangladesh to strengthen policy coherence and domestic resource mobilization that can align with global climate goals (CPD, 2025).

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restoration (UNFCCC, 2025; The Daily Star, 2024).

Success for Bangladesh at COP-30 will be measured by concrete outcomes: a finalized NCQG meeting developing-country needs (its quantum, balance, and transparency), substantial donor pledges to Loss and Damage, clear commitments on tech transfer mechanisms, official mention of climate mobility protections, and strengthened adaptation finance channels for LDCs.

Additionally, binding signals from major emitters to raise their NDCs – in line with 1.5°C – would mark real progress. These achievements will hinge on our ability to couple moral persuasion (as a front-line nation) with technical excellence and coalition clout.

The recent record of Bangladesh shows that it is possible. As CVF Chair, the country helped rally dozens of nations in the “Midnight Survival Deadline” and steered the Dhaka-Glasgow Declaration, proving it can set the agenda (ICCCAD, 2024). By applying those same strategies like coalition leadership, strong narratives, data-driven proposals, and diplomatic savvy — Bangladesh can ensure Belém 2025 yields decisive support for its people on the climate front lines. The survival of Bangladesh’s communities, and the credibility of the 1.5°C target, depend on it.

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